

Status quo of data integration and interoperability in German tourism

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Highlights

- Nowadays, data availability and its sustainable use play an important role in the tourism industry.
- Data, data management and data integration are already being dealt with intensively in the tourism industry, but the implementation and use of data is still lacking in some areas.
- For the sustainable use of data, it is essential to make data usable for various purposes, to facilitate the exchange of data and to make it available to both guests and service providers. However, the amount of open data has yet to be increased.
- In the future, many destinations and service providers are aiming towards a more comprehensive use of existing data.

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Introduction

The availability of a wide range of tourism-relevant data and the possibility of its further use and processing is becoming increasingly important for destination management. Developments, particularly in the field of artificial intelligence (AI), result in data becoming increasingly fluid and is no longer linked to a specific output channel. As a result, data must be prepared in such a way that it can be used in an interoperable manner (i.e. independently of the respective output channel). Thanks to new technological possibilities (e.g. generative AI or sensor technology), data is available in large quantities. However, this only offers added value if data is well-stored and -structured as well as made available openly. A strategically well-thought-out approach to using data ensures that it contributes to various goals and, in the best case, can be reused for many different purposes. The basis for this is laid by data management and its various tasks. Ensuring data interoperability is an important criterion.

This is important for the entire tourism industry and especially for digital visitor management. The AIR project therefore also deals intensively with the topic of data management. As part of the project, data is obtained from various data sources and processed for further use. The aim is also to find out more about data integration options and the current situation regarding data management and use in German tourism. Possible conclusions are to be derived and the knowledge gained made available to other interested parties. Seven guided interviews were conducted between November 8, 2023 and March 5, 2024 in the form of exchange discussions within the project, but also beyond the project, on the possibilities of data integration. The findings are presented in this short report. This is supplemented by further research results on theoretical backgrounds. The research was carried out following the interviews in order to substantiate

the statements made during the discussions with findings from the literature.

Data management and interoperability

Data management is now a high priority in tourism. However, this has not yet been implemented everywhere and there is still room for improvement in some areas. At destination level, data management can be an essential basis both for predominantly internal processes (e.g. the analysis of tourist behavior on site using sensor technology) and for communication and the quality of the guest experience (e.g. that guests can obtain digital information about locations, opening times, prices, etc. of PoI (Points of Interest) at any time). When implementing data management, the focus should therefore be on the readability, interpretability and usability of data for machines and humans (Horster, 2022, p. 613). However, the complex structures in the tourism industry due to the large number of stakeholders with their own needs and interests repeatedly pose challenges (Naschert et. al, 2023a, p. 5). This makes it all the more important that there is close coordination with regard to data generation, storage and maintenance to enable data integration and data exchange between different stakeholders and projects. This is also important because tourism, as a cross-sectoral industry, has a special responsibility here and sometimes also has to integrate stakeholders indirectly affected by tourism, such as retailers, parking management (often the responsibility of cities and municipalities) or residents, and is also dependent on data from these entities in some cases.

In this context, **data interoperability** is of great importance. This enables data to be stored, exchanged, retrieved and flexibly played out in different places without data loss or deployment problems (Horster, 2022, p. 619, 623). In this context, interoperability means that the data

can be linked to each other. . To achieve this, standardized data models (also known as ontologies) should be used. **Ontologies** ensure the uniform naming of data, as they define specifications for the standardized markup language of data. Data is entered with a corresponding semantic (uniform) description, which also simplifies the machine readability of the data (Fensel et al., 2020, p. 69 f.). The use of such **data models** then ensures that both humans and machines can interpret the data unambiguously. The goal of uniformly labeling the data is supported by the uniform description of objects (e.g. hotels), corresponding attributes (e.g. number of rooms) and the value ranges (e.g. availability). Internationally accepted standards (e.g. Schema.org or smartdatamodels.org) should be used as the basis for this (German National Tourist Board (GNTB), 2020, p. 52). This also facilitates the consolidation of different data in one or more data hubs and the exchange of data between them. In practice, however, inconsistent object descriptions, attributes, data types and value ranges sometimes make data integration more difficult (Naschert et. al, 2023a, p. 10). Manual maintenance or (partially) automated mappings can provide a remedy in this context. However, the former should ideally be avoided. **Mapping** is a largely automated process in data management that links different fields in the various data hubs. It also determines which data models are accepted by an interface and the form in which the data is passed on (e.g. Auer et al., 2013, p. 83 f.; Sequeda & Miranker, 2014, p. 95 f.). Ideally, the result of the mapping is that the data is then available in the predefined data model and is therefore interoperable by definition.

Data can be transferred both manually and automatically. Automated data transfer ensures that the data is prepared and transferred to the data infrastructure by defining (use case-specific) standards. In the case of manual data transfer, those responsible should be made aware of the need to enter data in accordance with the specifications (e.g. in meters instead

of kilometers) (Naschert et. al, 2023a, p. 15). If data is exchanged between different databases, it is also important to check whether the standards used are compatible and the transfer can therefore be carried out without the intermediate step of mapping and whether the quality is sufficient (Kudraß, 2015, p. 28). Here, too, it becomes clear that a standardized data model can simplify the transfer immensely.

The (automated) transfer of data is usually made possible by **interfaces**. In addition to data models, interfaces are therefore another important factor for data interoperability. In the software context, interfaces are also often known as application programming interfaces (API), which enable communication, data transfer and regular updating of data (e.g. Frank et al., 2021, p. 19; Geewax, 2023, p. 30 f.; Hack 2023; Winniewski, 2024, p. 9 f.). Using interfaces, data can either be "pushed" from the source system into one or more other systems or actively "pulled" from the source system by the respective external system. Regardless of the variant used, data can be transferred in full via interfaces. However, it is also possible to specify the data to be transferred if required (Kunde et al. 2018, p. 110 f.). It should be emphasized that interfaces are not mutually exclusive in the sense of "either or", but should rather be seen as complementary.

The **open availability of data** is also dependent on interfaces, as this makes it easier for different people to transfer data for different purposes (Naschert et. al, 2023a, p. 17). In this context, **open data** is an important pillar for the use and transfer of data and is usually ensured by open licensing in addition to the provision of an interface and the use of an established data model (Horster, 2022, p. 620). In line with the 5-star model for open data according to Berners-Lee (2012), this guarantees easy reuse.

The above points are essential, particularly in the context of digital visitor management, the use of digital guest cards in destinations and central data storage in data hubs. If data is not processed and maintained appropriately, isolated solutions are created that are no longer up to date and ensure that the potential and added value of data is not fully exploited and can benefit the destinations.

Interview results

As part of the interviews for Smart Destination Integration (work package 5 in the AIR project), digital solutions for visitor management systems in destinations and applications that also use tourism data were researched. Based on the research results, the function and activity level of potential contacts were then categorized in order to create a list of possible interview partners. The subsequent interviews made it possible to incorporate a broad spectrum of experience into the final situation assessment and integration logic. The findings of the interviews with representatives of three different data hubs, representatives of three digital spa and guest cards and a representative of a digital travel guide were summarized in eight questions, which are explained below:

What interests are there in expanding the database? What added value does this offer?

It was repeatedly made clear in the interviews that there is a **great deal of interest** overall in expanding the database (e.g. by integrating data from location measurements). The *data hubs in particular* see data integration as a good opportunity to facilitate an exchange of experience, **build a broad database** and **disseminate tourism data**. A similar interest was also expressed by the *digital spa and guest cards* and the *digital travel guide*. As expected, the integration of data generated in the AIR

project is only an option for some of the contact persons, as this data only relates to the six use cases in Schleswig-Holstein, North Rhine-Westphalia and Bavaria.

What are the requirements for the data?

In terms of the requirements for the data, it was mainly emphasized that it must be freely accessible under an **open data license** (CC-0, CC-BY, CC-BY-SA) so that data integration is generally possible. This applies to the *data hubs*, the *digital spa and guest maps as well as to the digital travel guide* and especially with regard to the use of the data for external display, while licenses that are not freely accessible are usually sufficient for use in internal or in-house applications. Although the importance of open data was repeatedly mentioned, the **proportion of freely accessible data** in the case of the *data hubs* surveyed is only **around 20 to 50%** according to their own estimates. These statements are consistent with the DMO DigitalMonitor 2023 (BTE, 2023¹). According to this, 40% of destinations make their digital data freely available to other users. In around 11% of destinations, digital data is made freely available at least within the destinations. It was also surprising that the requirements primarily relate to opening up under licensing law. Nevertheless, it has already been shown here that opening up the data in the sense of a linked open data approach according to Tim Berners-Lee (2012) also includes structuring the data in the form of an established data model, which is not yet the focus of the representatives surveyed.

¹ Data basis: Online survey of tourism organizations in Germany between 26.04.2023 - 14.06.2023; n= 483.

How does data integration work?

Data is integrated into the *data hubs* via an interface (**API**), for which API documentation is usually publicly available. Both a **push** and a **pull interface** are often possible, whereby the push interface is preferred here as the data does not have to be actively retrieved again and again.

The *digital spa and guest cards* often use **external databases** that are either managed and updated by the tourism service providers or are integrated via middleware that uses various interfaces with a data cruncher to standardize terms (**push interfaces**). A data cruncher is software that can quickly analyse and process large amounts of data, helping to standardize and organize different data sources. The same applies to the *digital travel guide*, where an intermediate database is used before the data is forwarded to the data hub.

How long must the data transmission interval be?

The intervals for data transfer **do not yet show any uniform procedures**. While the transmission interval for the *data hubs* is either linked to the specifications of the external service providers, there are no specifications or the data is pushed to the data hub in bundles every 24 hours, the data transmission intervals for the *digital spa and guest cards* in particular are only planned for the future or not at all. Only the *digital travel guide* pushes the data in real time to an intermediary database and a data hub. The data is then displayed on the company's own website at 15-

minute intervals. It is important to note that the need for updating depends heavily on the type of data in question. The master data of a hotel, for example, changes relatively rarely, whereas the current number of visitors to a swimming pool could be updated every minute.

Which data models/data standards are used?

If their own data models/data standards are used, the majority of the interviewed stakeholders and their institutions base their models/standards on the attributes of the **Open Data Tourism Alliance (ODTA)** or on **Schema.org**. In addition, one *data hub* has set **its own quality standards** to ensure a minimum level of quality when entering and transferring data. Furthermore, two of the three data hubs use **mapping** as an intermediate step, which has proven to be a valuable process for adapting the data to the ODTA data model. Accordingly, this is particularly important if data has not been entered in accordance with the models used and is therefore aligned via the mapping.

How is the data played out?

The *data hubs* primarily use **progressive web apps (PWAs)** within their own channels. In addition to the general information for the PoI, capacity utilization is also displayed in some cases. Dashboards that provide an overview of visitor flows and capacity utilization in a B2B context are also already being implemented or are at least planned. In addition, there are collaborations with various commercial and non-commercial providers who display the data in the respective data hub on their own applications.

The *digital travel guide* also enables the external display of dynamic and static data via a **PWA** and for internal partners using **dashboard access**. The PWA allows the data to be displayed on digital screens at tourist

attractions as well as on their websites. Capacity utilization displays with **traffic light systems** are currently still being planned. It can therefore be expected that live data will also be displayed directly on site in the future.

What are the implementation challenges?

During the interviews, it emerged that data integration and interoperability is associated with a number of challenges. In particular, the **lack of human resources** in connection with the **high effort required to ensure data quality and maintenance** leads to a lengthy process. At the same time, there are often **many parties involved** who not only need to be made aware of the usefulness of the project, but who in some cases are also **not interested**, which often makes the work more difficult. This is nevertheless understandable, as it is an abstract topic that cannot always be clarified through various deployment channels and the effects of data maintenance on them.

Other challenges mentioned included the fact that in many cases there are **no open data licenses** for the data, it is **very difficult to install your own sensors to collect data** and there are **digitization inhibitors due to signatures on registration forms**, meaning that important data could be lost in some cases.

Conclusions

Situation assessment based on the interviews

The results of the interviews on smart destination integration were first divided into the three categories of data transfer, data models and display for the situation assessment in Figure 1. An assessment was then carried out based on the degree of use in practice and prospective use.

Illustration 1: Situation evaluation matrix of the interview results

When looking at the matrix and the situation assessment, it should be noted that open data is seen as a basic prerequisite and overarching aspect and was therefore not included as a single aspect in Figure 1. It should also be noted that Schema.org forms the basis of the ODTA data model. Nevertheless, it is a specification that is tailored to the needs of tourism (domain specification). For this reason, both were included separately in the matrix (Figure 1) and in the situation assessment (Table 1).

The open availability of data plays a key role in many destinations and systems. This was also evident in the interviews conducted. In practice, the degree of utilization is around 0.5, but there is a strong interest in significantly increasing this proportion in the future. In terms of interfaces, both *push* and *pull interfaces* are used, but the latter much less frequently than the push interfaces. According to the discussions held,

however, it is also unlikely that this will change significantly. Nevertheless, APIs and databases generally enjoy relatively broad acceptance among practitioners and will probably continue to be used in the future. While the use of *data crunchers* is currently still rather low and no concrete prospects for future use were mentioned, around half of practitioners already use *mappings* in the area of data transfer. Regardless of the type and method of data transfer, however, *real-time transfer* is particularly important to the interviewees. Even if this has not yet been implemented in many cases, a possible transmission of real-time data is desired in almost all regions.

In terms of the **data models** used, the *ODTA standard* stands out. It is highly relevant and is currently either already used by almost all interviewees or will play a role in future plans. In comparison, *Schema.org* is used less frequently as an independent standard, although it is also the basis of the ODTA data model. Nevertheless, the original Schema.org vocabulary can also be combined with the ODTA data model, which is also done in practice simply because it is part of the ODTA data model. In addition, in German Tourism *own standards* also play an important role. With regard to the **deployment** of data, it has been shown that the main focus is on *PWAs and apps*, the *company's own website* and *dashboards*. This is also likely to be the case in future plans. However, *digital screens* can also already be found in some destinations and are used to display information. Of particular interest in this context is the display of *occupancy rates* and *live data* in order to actively guide visitors in the respective travel situation. This is not yet the case in all destinations, but the interviewees consider it important in the future.

The assessment of the situation so far is based on the results of the seven interviews conducted and therefore only serves as an example of the overall situation of smart destination integration in Germany. However,

the heterogeneous selection of interviewees provides a good initial overview of this context. This assessment of the situation is subsequently supplemented by further research findings. Although these aspects were not explicitly mentioned in the interviews, it can be assumed that some of them are already being used in practice and will become more relevant in the future.

Supplementary situation assessment

In the area of data models, smart data models should also be considered in (German) tourism, as the free-to-use models are compatible with standards such as Schema.org and have been prepared for various contexts (e.g. Arman et al., 2021, p. 8). General ontologies can be applied to specific use cases, such as digital visitor management, through specification (domain specifications) (Horster, 2022, p. 653). Such a specification has already been implemented as part of the LABTOUR-SH research project, whereby the Smart Data Models, Schema.org and the ODTA data model were used to develop the data model. Both the LABTOUR-SH data model and the ODTA data model are publicly available on the GitHub platform: www.github.com/LAB-TOUR-SH/dvm; <https://github.com/ODTA>.

However, before data integration and interoperability can be discussed in principle, *data quality, data density, data accuracy, data continuity and the universal usability* of the data should first be ensured. The best way to do this is through *open data storage* and *modern data management* (Naschert et al., 2023a, p. 5). This can also be used to directly attempt to ensure the machine readability of the data. *Machine readability* can lead to process optimization and simplified sustainable use of the data and, above all, supports the interoperability of the data. Nowadays, the goal should no longer be to prepare your own data exclusively for your own

websites, but to enable it to be played out on a wide variety of channels in the sense of a "headless web" approach (Horster & Kärle, 2019).

Other important foundations for data integration are the implementation of a *knowledge graph* for German tourism and the development of the *data infrastructure*. Knowledge graphs have several advantages over (relational) databases. Due to their structure in nodes and edges, heterogeneous and decentralized data can be linked together and thus made usable for different purposes and actors (e.g. Bellomarini et al., 2020, p. 25 f.; Hogan et al., 2021, p. 4 f.; Peng et al., 2023, p. 13073). Relational databases focus less on linking the different data and, if they do, this usually requires considerably more effort (Horster, 2022, p. 624). Both the use of suitable graph databases and the development of a comprehensive data infrastructure should ensure that the data is as interchangeable as possible. In concrete terms, this means that the different hubs must be compatible with each other in order to be able to integrate and pass on a variety of different data. The *data flows* should be able to take place in different directions and be made possible through the use of standardized interfaces and models (Sommer, 2018, p. 5).

Data maintenance (strategy) is important to ensure the long-term usability and added value of the data basis. This should include defining responsibilities and procedures so that the data is regularly checked for accuracy, up-to-dateness, etc. (Naschert et al. 2023a, p. 15). Some destinations have already committed to a corresponding strategy in German tourism.

A large database and the corresponding handling of it offers destinations a multitude of opportunities, even beyond visitor management (e.g. resource planning). The more data is available and the more accurate it is,

the more accurate the digital image of the (tourism) reality in the destination will be. This creates a virtual copy of the destination in the form of a *digital twin*.

According to Berners-Lee (2012), in addition to licenses, ontologies and data linking, the *data format* is also essential for the processing and transfer of data. This refers on the one hand to the format in which the data is available and on the other hand to the output format. Well-known formats in this context are XML, CSV or JSON-LD, some of which are already used in the destinations. Non-proprietary formats that are also capable of Linked Open Data, such as JSON-LD, are considered open formats.

The aforementioned points in the context of data management and data transmission enable a wide range of data to be played out – even beyond the deployment channels and content specified by the destinations. Especially with regard to digital visitor management, the *recommendation of alternative PoI* can lead to considerable added value. A few destinations are already suggesting alternative PoI or alternative visit periods in the event of high capacity utilization, and even more are aiming to do so in the long term. The aim is to reduce crowding and the associated negative effects on destinations (e.g. Schmücker et al., 2023, p. 294)

Overall, the use of AI will play an increasingly important role in the future. The development of AI is making great strides and can create new opportunities in terms of data integration and interoperability to optimize processes and make it easier for both humans and machines to deal with the variety of data. However, these developments also make it clear that proprietary and high-quality data, prepared in a form as described in this article, will play a decisive role in the development of corresponding AI-supported applications.

Table 1 provides an overview of the situation assessment based on the interviews (blue) and further research and expertise (green):

Table 1: Situation assessment of the use in practice and perspective use

Outlook

In the future, it will be important to navigate the tension between the status quo, the goals and the possibilities of data integration in tourism. A balanced understanding of what is actually being done, what should be achieved and what resources are available for this is crucial.

Currently, the focus in many places is primarily on displaying content in order to reach guests. However, the handling of data and, above all, its sustainable use should be given greater attention in the future. This is also reflected in the fact that the quantity of data currently often takes precedence over its quality. While a large amount of data may initially seem desirable, it is important not to collect data indiscriminately, as this can have a negative impact not only on the use but also on the quality of the data. Destinations often lack the resources (both human and financial) to ensure sufficient data maintenance. The lack of data maintenance can lead to the data quickly becoming outdated and the overview of the data being lost. The first step should therefore be to clearly define the objective that is to be achieved with the data. In the long term, this can help to ensure that the data can be maintained and used more effectively and efficiently. Expanding data expertise in destinations and raising awareness of the importance and benefits of data will be essential in German tourism in the future.

References

- Arman, Ala; Bellini, Pierfrancesco; Bologna, Daniele; Nesi, Paolo; Pantaleo, Gianni & Paolucci, Michela (2021). Automating IoT Data Ingestion Enabling Visual Representation. In: *Sensors*, 21(24), 8429. DOI: 10.3390/s21248429.
- Auer, Sören; Lehmann, Jens; Ngonga Ngomo, Axel-Cyrille; Stadler, Claus; Unbehauen, Jörg (2013): Extraktion, Mapping und Verlinkung von Daten im Web. In: *Datenbank-Spektrum*, 13(2), S. 77–87. DOI: 10.1007/s13222-013-0124-z.
- Bellomarini, Luigi; Sallinger, Emanuel & Vahdati, Sahar (2020). Knowledge Graphs: The Layered Perspective. In: Janev, Valentina; Graux, Damien; Jabeen, Hajira & Sallinger, Emanuel (eds.): *Knowledge Graphs and Big Data Processing*. Cham: Springer Nature, pp. 20-34. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-53199-7.
- Berners-Lee, Tim (2012). *5 Sterne offene Daten*. Available online at www.5stardata.info/de, last checked on 15.05.2024.
- BTE, 2023: DMO DigitalMonitor. Available online at <https://www.bte-tourismus.de/publikationen/dmo-digital-monitor/>, last checked on 22.07.2024.
- Fensel, Dieter; Şimşek, Umutcan; Angele, Kevin; Huaman, Elwin; Panasiuk, Oleksandra, Toma, Ioan; Umbrich, Jürgen & Wahler, Alexander (2020). *Knowledge Graps. Methodology, Tools and Selected Use Cases*. Cham: Springer Nature. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-37439-6.
- Frank, Roland; Strugholtz, Sebastian & Meise, Fabian (2021). *Bausteine der digitalen Transformation – Wie APIs Unternehmen den Weg in die Programmable Economy ebnet*. Wiesbaden: Springer Gabler.
- Geewax, J. J. (2023). *API Design Patterns*. Manning Publications Co. LLC.
- Hack, Carsten (2023). Definition. Was ist eine Schnittstelle (API)? In: *digitalmagazin*, 18.08.2023. Available online at <https://digitalmagazin.de/definition-was-ist-eine-schnittstelle-api/>, last checked on 07.12.2023.
- Hogan, Aidan; Blomqvist, Eva; Cochez, Michael; D'amato, Claudia; De Melo, Gerard; Gutierrez, Claudio; Kirrane, Sabrina; Gayo, José; Rashid, Sabbir; Rula, Anisa; Schmelzeisen, Lukas; Sequeda, Juan; Staab, Steffen & Zimmermann, Antoine (2021). Knowledge graphs. In: *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 54(4), pp. 1-37. DOI: 10.1145/3447772.
- Horster, Eric & Kärle, Elias (2019). *Das Headless Web*. Datenmanagement modular denken. Available online at <https://www.OpenData-germany.org/headless-web>, last checked on 08.05.2024.
- Horster, Eric; Honig, Kristine; Kärle, Elias & Bauhuber, Florian (2020). *Open Data im Deutschlandtourismus. Ein Wegweiser zur digitalen Destination* (on behalf of Deutsche Zentrale für Tourismus e.V.). Available online at www.OpenData-germany.org/handbuch-OpenData, last checked on 15.05.2024.

Horster, Eric (2022). *Digitales Tourismusmarketing*. Grundlagen, Suchmaschinenmarketing, User-Experience-Design, Social-Media-Marketing und Mobile Marketing. 1st ed. 2022. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden; Imprint: Springer Gabler.

Kudraß, Thomas (2015). *Taschenbuch Datenbanken*. 2. Auflage. München: Hanser.

Kunde, Felix; Pieper, Stephan & Sauer, Petra (2018). Datenmanagement von Echtzeit-Verkehrsdaten. In: Manuel Wiesche, Petra Sauer, Jürgen Krimmling und Helmut Krcmar (Hg.): *Management digitaler Plattformen: Konzeption und Realisierung eines offenen Ökosystems für intelligente Mobilitätsdienste in der Smart City*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, pp. 109–123.

Naschert, Lisa; Brinkmann, Alexander; Engelhardt, Denise; Höftmann, Nele; Horster, Eric; Krieg, Vincent; Mill, Colin; Radzio, Frank; Reif, Julian; Sjut, Boje & von Boguszewski, Niklas (2023a). *Datenmanagement und -infrastruktur im Rahmen des digitalen Besucher*innenmanagements*. Hg. v. Deutschen Institut für Tourismusforschung. Heide/Holstein (Ratgeber zum digitalen Besucher*innenmanagement, 3). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8063605.

Peng, Ciyuan; Xia, Feng; Naseriparsa, Mehdi; Osborne, Francesco (2023). Knowledge Graphs: Opportunities and Challenges. In: *Artificial Intelligence Review* 56, 13071-13102. DOI: 10.1007/s10462-023-10465-9.

Sequeda, Juan & Miranker, Daniel (2014). Mapping Relational Databases to Linked Data. In: Harth, Andreas; Hose, Katja & Schenkel, Ralf (eds.), *Linked Data Management - Emerging Directions in Database Systems and Applications*, pp. 95 - 116. CRC Press LCC.

Schmücker, Dirk; Keller, Robert; Reif, Julian; Schubert, Johannes & Sommer, G. (2023). Digitales Besuchermanagement im Tourismus – Konzeptioneller Rahmen und Gestaltungsmöglichkeiten. In: Gardini, Marco & Sommer, Guido (Hg.), *Digital Leadership im Tourismus: Digitalisierung und Künstliche Intelligenz als Wettbewerbsfaktoren der Zukunft*, S. 293–315. Springer Gabler.

Sommer, Guido (2018). *Herausforderungen und Chancen einer offenen digitalen Dateninfrastruktur im Tourismus: Ergebnisse des ersten Think Tank zu Open Data im Tourismus und aktuelle Entwicklungen*. Available online at <http://www.OpenData-germany.org/sommer-2018>, last checked on 08.05.2024.

Winniewski, Philipp (2024). *Grundlagenwissen der Software-Entwicklung. IT-Konzepte und Fachbegriffe für das Projektmanagement*. Wiesbaden: Springer Nature.

Notes

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